

Historical Dictionary of Latvian Given Names (LAnDe project)

Version 1

Description

The aim of the project Latvian Anthroponymic Desiderata: diachronic research of unexplored Latvian given names for global integration and open access (LAnDe) (No. zp-2025/1-0125, project lead Renāte Siliņa-Piņķe) is to bring Latvian personal name material into the international scholarly circle through the study of 13th to 16th century sources that have not been linguistically analysed so far. The plan is (1) to excerpt and systematise given names data from 20 to 25 sources or sets of sources dating from the 13th to 16th century, (2) to carry out a study on the development of Latvian given names during this period on the basis of the obtained material and scientific literature; (3) to publish the results of the study as open access in at least three articles and in a minimum of 300 entries of the electronic Historical Dictionary of Latvian Given Names (LPVW); (4) on the basis of the insights and research gaps identified, prepare and submit a new project application to a national research and development project competition, (5) to improve the search engine of LPVW and to develop an educational game. The planned project outputs: at least three Scopus articles, 300 entries in the LPVW (origin, historical development, source examples, parallel forms, etc.), a new project application, and a digital educational game. The overarching aim of the project is to ensure the continuity of the temporarily interrupted research on personal names in line with the National Language Policy Framework Plan 2021-2027, and to develop an innovative solution in the field of digital humanities that would allow for the development of further solutions in historical research on language.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Latvian Anthroponymic
Desiderata: Diachronic
research of unexplored Latvian
given names for global
integration and open access
(LAnDe)(zp-2025/1-0125)

Researchers

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0009-9247-605X, 0009-0002-8316-8628

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Historical Dictionary of Latvian Given Names \(LAnDe project\)](#)

Description:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science | | LCS](#)

Grants: [Latvian Anthroponymic Desiderata: Diachronic research of unexplored Latvian given names for global integration and open access \(LAnDe\)\(zp-2025/1-0125\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-29](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Historical Dictionary of Latvian Given Names

The electronic dictionary (LPVV) will be a systematic and scientifically processed compilation of original and published data from various historical sources that contain information on the names of Latvian people: (1) data from the Central Statistical Bureau of the Republic of Latvia, also published on its website at <https://tools.csb.gov.lv/names/en/0/0/20>; and (2) electronically processed data from other sources in the ranked list of historical sources from the 13th–16th centuries, such as documents, revisions, lists, etc. The collected and processed data will be used in writing the LPVV. They will be scientifically analyzed and described, and published as electronic dictionary.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Latvian given name data from historical sources and their publications from different periods will be collected to study the diachronic distribution of Latvian given names and to write entries for the Historical Dictionary of Latvian Given Names (LPVV).

The main sources are: (1) various collections of medieval documents from Vidzeme and Kurzeme (LUB, LGU, KGCh); (2) editions of documents on the history of Riga's economy (RS, LR, EBR, VBLR), (3) publications of various shorter documents.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

online dictionary

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

n/a

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful to the researchers and students (especially in the fields of linguistics – onomastics, sociolinguistics, language contacts; history; cultural

studies; human geography; translation studies, etc.); library, archive, museum professionals; educators and learners; research-based writers, artists; history and family history enthusiasts.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Handle

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

any internet browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-12-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Renāte Siliņa-Piņķe (orcid: [0000-0002-5553-2165](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5553-2165))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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